

Arsenic and Metal Contamination in Stream Sediments and Waters of Kyaukpahto Mine Area, Kawlin Township, Sagaing Division

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Abstract

Stream sediments and waters samples were studied for arsenic and metal contamination around the Kyaukpahto mine area. Sediments of the Kyauk Ohe Chaung has arsenic contamination of 24-35 ppm, where as the regional background is 0.1 ppm to 1.6 ppm. The origin of arsenic in mining waste disposal is from arsenopyrite. Surfacewater and tailings show arsenic and zinc concentrations are higher than WHO (World Health Organization) drinking water guidelines. Groundwater samples show arsenic and zinc concentrations below WHO guideline. Waters interacting with the ore deposit are generally non-acidic, likely due to the low sulphidation system. Non-acidic environment does not favor the mobility of elements associated with the mineralization, such as Zn and As. In addition, aqueous transport of these elements seems limited by the precipitation of ferrihydrite, which is able to reduce or remove these elements, particularly As, from solution of the Kyaukpahto mine area.

Key words: Arsenic, stream sediments, waters, mining wastes, contamination

Introduction

The Kyaukpahto gold mine is the first open pit gold mine in Myanmar. There has been extensive gold mining activity in this area since early 1982. The reserves were estimated at approximately 6 million tons at an average grade of 3.0 g/t Au with a cut-off grade of 1.0g/t (Saw Maung et al., 1991). In the past mining activity, when tailing pumps broke down and as well as flooded over the tailing dam, all of ore processing residues were discharged into the headwaters of the Kyauk Ohe Chuang. Possible major pollutants are from the natural geology source and chemical reagents in tailing from gold processing plant. Due to these mining activities in this area, the problems of the potential harmful elements contamination such as As, Cd, Zn, Sb and CN in the mill tailing, water and stream sediments should be investigated as part of the environmental management programmed.

The Study Area

The study area is situated in Kawlin Township, Sagaing Division, 26 km east of Kawlin and 195 km north of Mandalay (Figure 1). The mining activities began since 1982 and in the past mining activity; approximately produced 3 million tons of ores were milled. Currently Eternal Group Company made a sound technical system and to improve gold recoveries at the Kyaukpahto gold mine. The area contains many small rolling hills and in the plain region there are a few villages and cultivated area for the crop and paddy. As the area the mining activity continued for a long period and accidentally tailing dam flooded over to the Kyauk Ohe Chaung, an investigation on arsenic and metals contamination is important to understand the impact on the environment.

The Gold Mining Operation

In Kyaukpahto area, the mineralization is of stockwork and disseminated styles, closely associated with breccia zones within silicified sandstone of the Mela Formation. Open cut Mining activity began in the year 1991 and now the operating mine has been working at the depths of approximately 320 m below the surface. The gold is recovered by cyanidation and cyanide heap-leach processing methods.

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Figure 1. The study area

Figure 2. Location map of stream sediment samples

In Kyaukpahto gold deposit, mineral graphic and SEM-EDS analyses of both solid ore and mill products indicate that the most common refractoriness of Kyaukpahto ore is caused by fine gold encapsulation in pyrite and quartz (silica-locked Au), and also invisible gold present in the sulphides. Gold is still interlocked or encapsulated in pyrite even in -250 # fraction and is also present as invisible gold in the matrix of pyrite (Cho Cho Aye, 2006). This type of ore needs roasting or bio-oxidation prior to cyanide leaching (Ye Myint Swe, 2004).

In April 2008, No.2 Mining Ministry was handover to Eternal Group Company. Eternal Group Company made a sound technical system to improve the mine operation and ore production. The following table shows the ore production at Kyaukpahto in the past mining activities and the amount of ores remaining under present time operation.

Table.1 The amount of ore productions in the past mining activities and present operation

Mining Design	Current extraction	Remaining ores
6.14 Mt	2.26 Mt	3.38 Mt

Table.2 The comparison of ores capacities between past and present mining activities

(1991 - 2007)	(2008 - present)
350 t/day – 500 t/day	700 t/day – 1000 t/day
Storage capacity for stock piles 40,000 t/month	Storage capacity for stock piles 100,000 t/month

The Samples and Analytical Method

The selected eleven stream sediments were analyzed by using the graphic furnace atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS) in Department of Applied Geology, Yangon University.

Six surface-water samples were collected from the Kyauk Ohe Chaung and six groundwater samples from six domestic wells tapped into Kyauk Ohe Chaung (Figure 3). Water samples were analyzed for trace metals, including As, Zn and Sb.

Arsenic was determined by the arsenator. The arsenator system is the lowest cost, most portable and accurate method for determining arsenic in safe limits (WHO guide-lines 10 ppb/ $\mu\text{g/l}$).

The arsenator is the world's first digital field instrument capable of measuring arsenic in water down to ppb levels. Arsenator method is reliable, accurate and precise method although it is a field measurement method and gives accurate test results between the critical range of $2\mu\text{g/l}$ (ppb) to $100\mu\text{g/l}$ (ppb).

Zn and Sb were analyzed by the graphic furnace atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS) in Department of applied Geology, Yangon University, Yangon. The concentration of As, Zn and Sb present in water samples were compared with the drinking water guidelines of WHO (1993).

Figure 3. Locations map of the water samples

Figure 4. Anomaly map of As contamination in different types of stream sediments of the Kyaukpahto mine area

Results and Discussion

The Kyaukpahto stockworks/disseminated style, arsenic rich, epithermal ore body is reflected in the tailing disposal along the Kyauk Ohe Chaung. The arsenic contamination of the mine-derived sediments deposited along the Kyauk Ohe Chaung has shown in the Table 3.

Table 3. As and Cd contamination of stream sediments in the mine site and Kuauk Ohe Chaung

	mine site								villages		
	ore feed rocks plant S1	flotation plant S2	cynadation plant S3	divert channel S4	mine entrance S5	mine entrance S6	mine site S7	downstream of tailing dam S8	Ban bwe gone S9	Swe ya S10	Sein pan gone S11
As	24	23	30	28	35	35	22	28	28	28	27
Cd	0.16	0.33	0.28	0.17	0.45	0.47	0.32	0.26	0.26	0.17	0.25

Notes: all the values in ppm

Table 4. As contamination of stream sediments in Shauk Cho Gon (Regional Background Values) Newmont, 1996

	Alluvium working down stream	Male Sand stone	Minor mudstone	Shallow dips	No alter No vein	Shauk Cho Gon Chaung			
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9
As	0.5	1	0.1	0.8	1.3	1.4	1	1.2	1.6

Notes: all the values in ppm

Table 5. As contamination of stream sediments in Kyaukpahto NE extension (Anomaly values) Newmont, 1996

	Trib fr L	Main stream R	Trib fr L	Main stream R											
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10	S11	S12	S13	S14	S15
As	12.8	3.8	4.8	3.1	3	2.4	2.3	3.1	3.2	3.6	3	3	12.7	2.5	3.5

Notes: all the values in ppm

Figure 5. The range of the As contaminations in different types of stream sediments.
Codes: 1. Background stream sediments
2. Anomaly stream sediments
3. Polluted stream sediments

Table 7. Concentrations of metals in the water samples

Sample name	As	Zn	Sb
WHO drinking water guideline	10.00	3.00	0.005
S1	40.00	3.45	0.150
S2	44.00	2.15	0.017
S3	44.00	1.45	0.014
S4	24.00	2.18	0.009
S5	22.00	1.67	0.011
S6	0.000	1.34	0.012
W1	5.00	2.16	0.015
W2	1.00	1.87	0.014
W3	0.000	1.89	0.011
W4	0.000	2.34	0.013
W5	0.000	2.15	0.012
W6	0.000	2.34	0.011
MG	>100.0	4.39	0.042
TP	>100.0	10.58	0.067

Notes: As concentration is in µg/L or ppb and Zn and Sb concentrations are mg/L or ppm

Figure 4 and 5 show that the anomaly map of As contaminations from different types of stream sediments in Kyaukpahto mine area and the range of the As contents in different stream sediments types.

According to the As anomaly map As contamination is similarly distributed along the downstream of the Kyauk Ohe Chaung, from the in front of mine site to until the flooded plain area. It is shown that the mine derived sediments were drained through the Kyauk Ohe Chaung and deposited in the flood plain, the paddy fields around the Swe-ya village.

The concentration of As, Zn and Sb present in water samples were compared with the drinking water guidelines of WHO (1993). The difference in identified contaminants between water samples from surface water, groundwater, tailing, and mine drainage water (Table 7). The water samples analyses show the value metals in the Kyauk Ohe Chaung higher than the drinking water guidelines of WHO. Groundwater samples in the study area show metal concentrations are below the WHO drinking water guidelines.

Arsenic – Analyses results from water samples, Kyauk Ohe Creek water, mine ground water and tailings, show higher the WHO guideline. In general, As contamination in water samples from Kyauk Ohe Creek appeared to be higher in the areas closer to the mine site, and gradually decrease in downstream (Fig.6). High concentrations of As occur at the tailing pond (TP) and mine drainage water (MG).

These studies show that arsenic was originated from the arsenopyrite (FeAsS) in ores and mining wastes at the mine site. The source of arsenic in water samples is related to arsenic-sulfide minerals such as arsenopyrite. The arsenic was transported by Kyauk Ohe Chaung as primary sulfides in the crushed mine tailings. After release by the oxidation of sulfides, arsenic was reattached to the floodplain sediments in association with oxide and hydroxide minerals. It could then become soluble under oxidizing conditions (Drever, 1997).

The previous study shows that a substantial amount of arsenic was found in the stream sediments of the Kyauk Ohe Chaung. The arsenic in surface water significantly reflected the mining activity, flooded Kyauk Ohe Chaung by tailing disposal probably the concentrations in stream sediments. Accidentally release of tailings during the past mining activities 1997-2007.

Figure 6. Concentration of Arsenic in the water samples

Figure 7. Concentration of Zinc in the water samples

Zinc – Analyses water samples show Zn concentration below the WHO guideline (Table 7). Under low pH conditions, Zn is immobile and dissolved Zn values higher in acidic mine drainage is draining from oxidation of pyrite and sphalerite rich ores. In Kyaukpahto gold mine, Zn concentrations show 10.58 ppm in the tailing is originating from the minerals sphalerite in the ores. Anomaly map of Zn concentration in the water samples has shown in the (Figure 7).

Conclusion

According to the analyses results of stream sediments, there has been past gold mining activity in Kyaukpahto mine area, was resulting in impacts on the environment by mining waste disposals. Stream sediments of the Kyauk Ohe Chaung show As contamination of 22

ppm and up to 35 ppm, where as the regional background is 0.1 ppm to 1.6 ppm and anomaly values from NE extension of Kyaukpahto mineralized zone is 2.3 ppm to 12.8 ppm (after Newmont, 1996). When the tailing pump broken down and as well as overflow on tailings dam, the mine dumps were dispersed into the surrounding environments by Kyauk Ohe Chaung (surface runoff) and by wind-suspended particles.

From the analyses results of water samples, As and Zn contamination in the Kyauk Ohe Chaung near the mine site show the value higher than the WHO guide line. No contamination show in the groundwater in the villages around the mine site. At the mine site village, As contamination in groundwater is 1-5 ppb and lower than the WHO drinking water guideline. Their surface water and ground water contamination levels appeared to be higher in the area closer to the mine site, and to decrease toward the downstream area. The ultimate source of arsenic in water resources might be arsenopyrite. The dissolved arsenic underwent adsorption-desorption processes with amorphous iron, Fe(OH₃). The arsenic level in the Kyauk Ohe Chaung water indicating that adsorption on and desorption from Fe-oxyhydroxides could contribute to the arsenic concentration in water.

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